

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321385477>

Jaccard Vector Similarity Measure of Bipolar Neutrosophic Set Based on Multi-Criteria Decision Making

Conference Paper · March 2016

CITATIONS

10

READS

31

3 authors:

Memet Şahin

Gaziantep University

67 PUBLICATIONS 191 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Irfan Deli

Kilis 7 Aralık Üniversitesi

72 PUBLICATIONS 1,218 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Vakkas Uluçay

42 PUBLICATIONS 153 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Symmetric Derivations, Exterior Derivation [View project](#)

New Trends in Neutrosophic Theory and Applications [View project](#)

Jaccard Vector Similarity Measure of Bipolar Neutrosophic Set Based on Multi-Criteria Decision Making

Mehmet Şahin

Gaziantep University, Department of Mathematics, Gaziantep 27310-Turkey

Irfan Deli

Kilis 7 Aralık University, Muallim Rıfat Faculty of Education, Kilis 79000, Turkey

Vakkas Uluçay

Gaziantep University, Department of Mathematics, Gaziantep 27310-Turkey

ABSTRACT

The main aim of this study is to present a novel method based on multi-criteria decision making for bipolar neutrosophic sets. Therefore, Jaccard vector similarity and weighted Jaccard vector similarity measure is defined to develop the bipolar neutrosophic decision making method. In addition, the method is applied to a numerical example in order to confirm the practicality and accuracy of the proposed method.

Keywords: Neutrosophic set, bipolar neutrosophic set, Jaccard vector similarity measure, multi-criteria decision making.

1. Introduction

As generalization of fuzzy set [20] and intuitionistic fuzzy set [1], Smarandache [10,11] initiated the notation of neutrosophic set which has a truth-membership, a indeterminacy membership and a false-membership function in $^{-}[0,1]^+$. After Smarandache, many extensions and examples of neutrosophic sets have been introduced by many researcher such as; single valued neutrosophic sets [13], interval neutrosophic sets [14], single valued neutrosophic multi-sets [5,16], N-valued interval neutrosophic sets [2], neutrosophic soft sets [9], interval neutrosophic soft sets [7], possibility neutrosophic soft sets [8], rough neutrosophic sets [12], and so on. As a significant content in fuzzy sets, the similarity measure between the these sets have received more attention to calculate the degree of similarity measure between proposed the sets in [2,3,4,12,15,17,18,19].

Recently, different a generalization of neutrosophic sets is proposed by Deli et a.[6] is called bipolar neutrosophic sets. The bipolar neutrosophic set can be effectively used to evaluate information during decision making process. Therefore, in this study we present a novel method by extending the Jaccard vector similarity measures of neutrosophic sets to bipolar neutrosophic sets.

2. Preliminaries

In the subsection, we give some concepts related to neutrosophic sets and bipolar neutrosophic sets.

Definition 2.1 [10-11] Let X be a universe of discourse. Then a neutrosophic set N is defined as:

$$N = \{(x, F_N(x), T_N(x), I_N(x)): x \in X\},$$

which is characterized by a truth-membership function $T_N: X \rightarrow]0^-, 1^+[$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_N: X \rightarrow]0^-, 1^+[$ and a falsity-membership function $F_N: X \rightarrow]0^-, 1^+[$.

There is not restriction on the sum of $T_N(x)$, $I_N(x)$ and $F_N(x)$, so $0^- \leq \sup T_N(x) \leq \sup I_N(x) \leq \sup F_N(x) \leq 3^+$.

Definition 2.2 [15] Let X be a universe of discourse. Then a single valued neutrosophic set (SVN-set) is defined as:

$$N = \{ \langle x, F_N(x), T_N(x), I_N(x) \rangle : x \in X \},$$

which is characterized by a truth-membership function $T_N: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_N: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and a falsity-membership function $F_N: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

There is not restriction on the sum of $T_N(x)$, $I_N(x)$ and $F_N(x)$, so $0 \leq \sup T_N(x) \leq \sup I_N(x) \leq \sup F_N(x) \leq 3$.

Definition 2.3 [6] Let X be a universe of discourse. A bipolar neutrosophic set A_{BNS} in X is defined as an object of the form

$$A_{BNS} = \{ \langle x, T^+(x), I^+(x), F^+(x), T^-(x), I^-(x), F^-(x) \rangle : x \in X \},$$

where $T^+, I^+, F^+ : X \rightarrow [1, 0]$ and $T^-, I^-, F^- : X \rightarrow [-1, 0]$.

The positive membership degree $T^+(x), I^+(x), F^+(x)$ denotes the truth membership, indeterminate membership and false membership of an element $x \in X$ corresponding to a bipolar neutrosophic set A_{BNS} and the negative membership degree $T^-(x), I^-(x), F^-(x)$ denotes the truth membership, indeterminate membership and false membership of an element $x \in X$ to some implicit counter-property corresponding to a bipolar neutrosophic set A_{BNS} .

Set- theoretic operations, for two bipolar neutrosophic set

$$A_{BNS} = \{ \langle x, T_1^+(x), I_1^+(x), F_1^+(x), T_1^-(x), I_1^-(x), F_1^-(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

and

$$B_{BNS} = \{ \langle x, T_2^+(x), I_2^+(x), F_2^+(x), T_2^-(x), I_2^-(x), F_2^-(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$
 are given as;

1. The subset; $A_{BNS} \subseteq B_{BNS}$ if and only if

$$T_1^+(x) \leq T_2^+(x), I_1^+(x) \leq I_2^+(x), F_1^+(x) \geq F_2^+(x),$$

and

$$T_1^-(x) \geq T_2^-(x), I_1^-(x) \geq I_2^-(x), F_1^-(x) \leq F_2^-(x)$$

for all $x \in X$.

2. $A_{BNS} = B_{BNS}$ if and only if,

$$T_1^+(x) = T_2^+(x), I_1^+(x) = I_2^+(x), F_1^+(x) = F_2^+(x),$$

and

$$T_1^-(x) = T_2^-(x), I_1^-(x) = I_2^-(x), F_1^-(x) = F_2^-(x)$$

for all $x \in X$.

3. The complement of A_{BNS} is denoted by A_{BNS}^0 and is defined by

$$T_{A^c}^+(x) = \{1^+\} - T_A^+(x), I_{A^c}^+(x) = \{1^+\} - I_A^+(x), F_{A^c}^+(x) = \{1^+\} - F_A^+(x)$$

and

$$T_{A^c}^-(x) = \{1^-\} - T_A^-(x), I_{A^c}^-(x) = \{1^-\} - I_A^-(x), F_{A^c}^-(x) = \{1^-\} - F_A^-(x),$$

for all $x \in X$.

4. The intersection

$$(A_{BNS} \cap B_{BNS})(x) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \min(T_1^+(x), T_2^+(x)), \frac{I_1^+(x) + I_2^+(x)}{2}, \max((F_1^+(x), F_2^+(x)), \max(T_1^-(x), T_2^-(x))), \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \frac{I_1^-(x) + I_2^-(x)}{2}, \min((F_1^-(x), F_2^-(x))) \right\rangle : x \in X \right\}$$

5. The union

$$(A_{BNS} \cup B_{BNS})(x) = \left\{ \left\langle x, \max(T_1^+(x), T_2^+(x)), \frac{I_1^+(x) + I_2^+(x)}{2}, \min((F_1^+(x), F_2^+(x)), \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \min(T_1^-(x), T_2^-(x)), \frac{I_1^-(x) + I_2^-(x)}{2}, \max((F_1^-(x), F_2^-(x))) \right\rangle : x \in X \right\}.$$

Definition 2.3 [19] Let $A = \langle T_A(x_i), I_A(x_i), F_A(x_i) \rangle$ and $B = \langle T_B(x_i), I_B(x_i), F_B(x_i) \rangle$ be two SVN-sets in a universe of discourse $X = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$. Then the Jaccard similarity measure between SVN-sets A and B in the vector space is defined as follows:

$$J(A, B) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \times \left(\frac{T_A(x_i)T_B(x_i) + I_A(x_i)I_B(x_i) + F_A(x_i)F_B(x_i)}{\left[(T_A(x_i))^2 + (I_A(x_i))^2 + (F_A(x_i))^2 + (T_B(x_i))^2 + (I_B(x_i))^2 + (F_B(x_i))^2 \right] - (T_A(x_i)T_B(x_i) + I_A(x_i)I_B(x_i) + F_A(x_i)F_B(x_i))} \right)$$

Then, this similarity measure satisfies the following properties:

1. $0 \leq J(A, B) \leq 1$,
2. $J(A, B) = J(B, A)$,
3. $J(A, B) = 1$ for $A = B$ i.e. $T_A(x) = T_B(x), I_A(x) = I_B(x), F_A(x) = F_B(x), i = (1, 2, \dots, n) \in X$.

3. Jaccard vector similarity measure of Bipolar Neutrosophic Set

In this section, we present a Jaccard vector similarity and weighted Jaccard vector similarity measure for bipolar neutrosophic sets by extending the approach of SVN-set [19] to bipolar neutrosophic set.

Definition 3.1 Let $A = \langle T_A^+(x_i), I_A^+(x_i), F_A^+(x_i), T_A^-(x_i), I_A^-(x_i), F_A^-(x_i) \rangle$ and $B = \langle T_B^+(x_i), I_B^+(x_i), F_B^+(x_i), T_B^-(x_i), I_B^-(x_i), F_B^-(x_i) \rangle$ be two BNSs. Then, Jaccard similarity measure between BNS A and B, denoted $J(A, B)$, is defined as follows:

$$J(A, B) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \times \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{T_A^+(x_i)T_B^+(x_i) + I_A^+(x_i)I_B^+(x_i) + F_A^+(x_i)F_B^+(x_i) - (T_A^-(x_i)T_B^-(x_i) + I_A^-(x_i)I_B^-(x_i) + F_A^-(x_i)F_B^-(x_i))}{\left[(T_A^+(x_i))^2 + (I_A^+(x_i))^2 + (F_A^+(x_i))^2 + (T_B^+(x_i))^2 + (I_B^+(x_i))^2 + (F_B^+(x_i))^2 + (T_A^-(x_i))^2 + (I_A^-(x_i))^2 + (F_A^-(x_i))^2 + (T_B^-(x_i))^2 + (I_B^-(x_i))^2 + (F_B^-(x_i))^2 - (T_A^+(x_i)T_B^+(x_i) + I_A^+(x_i)I_B^+(x_i) + F_A^+(x_i)F_B^+(x_i)) - (T_A^-(x_i)T_B^-(x_i) + I_A^-(x_i)I_B^-(x_i) + F_A^-(x_i)F_B^-(x_i)) \right]} \right)$$

Definition 3.2 Let $A = \langle T_A^+(x_i), I_A^+(x_i), F_A^+(x_i), T_A^-(x_i), I_A^-(x_i), F_A^-(x_i) \rangle$ and $B = \langle T_B^+(x_i), I_B^+(x_i), F_B^+(x_i), T_B^-(x_i), I_B^-(x_i), F_B^-(x_i) \rangle$ be two BNSs and $w_i \in [0,1]$ be the weight of each element x_i for $i = (1,2, \dots, n)$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$. Then, weighted Jaccard similarity measure between BNS A and B, denoted $J_w(A, B)$, is defined as follows:

$$J_w(A, B) = \sum_{i=1}^n \times \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{w_i \left[\frac{T_A^+(x_i)T_B^+(x_i) + I_A^+(x_i)I_B^+(x_i) + F_A^+(x_i)F_B^+(x_i) - (T_A^-(x_i)T_B^-(x_i) + I_A^-(x_i)I_B^-(x_i) + F_A^-(x_i)F_B^-(x_i))}{\left[(T_A^+(x_i))^2 + (I_A^+(x_i))^2 + (F_A^+(x_i))^2 + (T_B^+(x_i))^2 + (I_B^+(x_i))^2 + (F_B^+(x_i))^2 + (T_A^-(x_i))^2 + (I_A^-(x_i))^2 + (F_A^-(x_i))^2 + (T_B^-(x_i))^2 + (I_B^-(x_i))^2 + (F_B^-(x_i))^2 - (T_A^+(x_i)T_B^+(x_i) + I_A^+(x_i)I_B^+(x_i) + F_A^+(x_i)F_B^+(x_i)) - (T_A^-(x_i)T_B^-(x_i) + I_A^-(x_i)I_B^-(x_i) + F_A^-(x_i)F_B^-(x_i)) \right]} \right]}{\left[(T_A^+(x_i))^2 + (I_A^+(x_i))^2 + (F_A^+(x_i))^2 + (T_B^+(x_i))^2 + (I_B^+(x_i))^2 + (F_B^+(x_i))^2 + (T_A^-(x_i))^2 + (I_A^-(x_i))^2 + (F_A^-(x_i))^2 + (T_B^-(x_i))^2 + (I_B^-(x_i))^2 + (F_B^-(x_i))^2 - (T_A^+(x_i)T_B^+(x_i) + I_A^+(x_i)I_B^+(x_i) + F_A^+(x_i)F_B^+(x_i)) - (T_A^-(x_i)T_B^-(x_i) + I_A^-(x_i)I_B^-(x_i) + F_A^-(x_i)F_B^-(x_i)) \right]} \right)$$

Proposition 3.3 Let $J_w(A, B)$ be a Jaccard similarity measure between bipolar neutrosophic sets A and B. Then, we have

1. $0 \leq J_w(A, B) \leq 1$,
2. $J_w(A, B) = J_w(B, A)$,
3. $J_w(A, B) = 1$ for $A = B$ i.e. $T_A^+(x_i) = T_B^+(x_i), I_A^+(x_i) = I_B^+(x_i), F_A^+(x_i) = F_B^+(x_i), T_A^-(x_i) = T_B^-(x_i), I_A^-(x_i) = I_B^-(x_i), F_A^-(x_i) = F_B^-(x_i) \quad i = (1,2, \dots, n) \in X$.

Proof:

1. It is clear from Definition 3.2.

2.

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_w(A, B) &= \sum_{i=1}^n \times \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{w_i \left[\frac{T_A^+(x_i)T_B^+(x_i) + I_A^+(x_i)I_B^+(x_i) + F_A^+(x_i)F_B^+(x_i) -}{(T_A^-(x_i)T_B^-(x_i) + I_A^-(x_i)I_B^-(x_i) + F_A^-(x_i)F_B^-(x_i))} \right]}{\left[\frac{(T_A^+(x_i))^2 + (I_A^+(x_i))^2 + (F_A^+(x_i))^2 + (T_B^+(x_i))^2 + (I_B^+(x_i))^2 + (F_B^+(x_i))^2 +}{(T_A^-(x_i))^2 + (I_A^-(x_i))^2 + (F_A^-(x_i))^2 + (T_B^-(x_i))^2 + (I_B^-(x_i))^2 + (F_B^-(x_i))^2} \right.} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. - (T_A^+(x_i)T_B^+(x_i) + I_A^+(x_i)I_B^+(x_i) + F_A^+(x_i)F_B^+(x_i)) \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. - (T_A^-(x_i)T_B^-(x_i) + I_A^-(x_i)I_B^-(x_i) + F_A^-(x_i)F_B^-(x_i)) \right] \right) \\
 &= \sum_{i=1}^n \times \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{w_i \left[\frac{T_B^+(x_i)T_A^+(x_i) + I_B^+(x_i)I_A^+(x_i) + F_B^+(x_i)F_A^+(x_i) -}{(T_B^-(x_i)T_A^-(x_i) + I_B^-(x_i)I_A^-(x_i) + F_B^-(x_i)F_A^-(x_i))} \right]}{\left[\frac{(T_B^+(x_i))^2 + (I_B^+(x_i))^2 + (F_B^+(x_i))^2 + (T_A^+(x_i))^2 + (I_A^+(x_i))^2 + (F_A^+(x_i))^2 -}{(T_B^-(x_i))^2 + (I_B^-(x_i))^2 + (F_B^-(x_i))^2 + (T_A^-(x_i))^2 + (I_A^-(x_i))^2 + (F_A^-(x_i))^2} \right.} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. - (T_B^+(x_i)T_A^+(x_i) + I_B^+(x_i)I_A^+(x_i) + F_B^+(x_i)F_A^+(x_i)) \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. - (T_B^-(x_i)T_A^-(x_i) + I_B^-(x_i)I_A^-(x_i) + F_B^-(x_i)F_A^-(x_i)) \right] \right) \\
 &= J_w(B, A).
 \end{aligned}$$

3. Since $T_A^+(x_i) = T_B^+(x_i), I_A^+(x_i) = I_B^+(x_i), F_A^+(x_i) = F_B^+(x_i), T_A^-(x_i) = T_B^-(x_i), I_A^-(x_i) = I_B^-(x_i), F_A^-(x_i) = F_B^-(x_i) \quad i = (1, 2, \dots, n) \in X$, we have $J_w(A, B) = 1$.

The proof is completed.

4. BN- Multi-criteria Decision Making Method

In this section, we developed BN- Multi-criteria Decision Making Method based on weighted Jaccard vector similarity for bipolar neutrosophic sets by extending the some definitions of SVN-set [19,21] to bipolar neutrosophic set.

Definition 4.1 Let $U = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m)$ be a set of alternatives, $A = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ be the set of criteria, $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ be the weight vector of the $a_j \quad (j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ such that $w_j \geq 0$ and $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$ and $[b_{ij}]_{m \times n} = \langle T_{ij}^+, I_{ij}^+, F_{ij}^+, T_{ij}^-, I_{ij}^-, F_{ij}^- \rangle$ be the decision matrix in which the rating values of the alternatives. Then

$$[b_{ij}]_{m \times n} = \begin{matrix} & a_1 & a_2 & \dots & a_n \\ \begin{matrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ \vdots \\ u_m \end{matrix} & \left(\begin{matrix} b_{11} & b_{12} & \dots & b_{1n} \\ b_{21} & b_{22} & \dots & b_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ b_{m1} & b_{m2} & \dots & b_{mn} \end{matrix} \right) \end{matrix}$$

is called a BN-multi-attribute decision making matrix of the decision maker.

Also; b_j^* is positive ideal bipolar neutrosophic solution of decision matrix $[b_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ as form:

$$b_j^* = \langle \max_i\{T_{ij}^+\}, \min_i\{I_{ij}^+\}, \min_i\{F_{ij}^+\}, \min_i\{T_{ij}^-\}, \max_i\{I_{ij}^-\}, \max_i\{T_{ij}^-\} \rangle$$

and \bar{b}_j^* is negative ideal bipolar neutrosophic solution of decision matrix $[b_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ as form:

$$\bar{b}_j^* = \langle \min_i\{T_{ij}^+\}, \max_i\{I_{ij}^+\}, \max_i\{F_{ij}^+\}, \max_i\{T_{ij}^-\}, \min_i\{I_{ij}^-\}, \min_i\{T_{ij}^-\} \rangle.$$

Algorithm:

Step1. Give the decision-making matrix $[b_{ij}]_{m \times n}$; for decision;

Step2. Compute the positive ideal (or negative ideal) bipolar neutrosophic solution $b_j^* = \{b_1^*, b_2^*, \dots, b_n^*\}$ for $[b_{ij}]_{m \times n}$;

Step3. Calculate the weighted Jaccard vector similarity measure S_i between positive ideal (or negative ideal) bipolar neutrosophic solution b_j^* and $b_i = \langle T_{ij}^+, I_{ij}^+, F_{ij}^+, T_{ij}^-, I_{ij}^-, F_{ij}^- \rangle$ and $(i = 1, 2, \dots, m)$ $(j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ as;

$$S_i = J_w(b_j^*, b_i) = \sum_{j=1}^n \times \left(\frac{w_i \left[\begin{matrix} (T_j^*)^+ (T_{ij}^*)^+ + (I_j^*)^+ (I_{ij}^*)^+ + (F_j^*)^+ (F_{ij}^*)^+ \\ (T_j^*)^- (T_{ij}^*)^- + (I_j^*)^- (I_{ij}^*)^- + (F_j^*)^- (F_{ij}^*)^- \end{matrix} \right]}{\left[\begin{matrix} ((T_j^*)^+)^2 + ((I_j^*)^+)^2 + ((F_j^*)^+)^2 + ((T_{ij}^*)^+)^2 + ((I_{ij}^*)^+)^2 + ((F_{ij}^*)^+)^2 \\ ((T_j^*)^-)^2 + ((I_j^*)^-)^2 + ((F_j^*)^-)^2 + ((T_{ij}^*)^-)^2 + ((I_{ij}^*)^-)^2 + ((F_{ij}^*)^-)^2 \\ -((T_j^*)^+ (T_{ij}^*)^+ + (I_j^*)^+ (I_{ij}^*)^+ + (F_j^*)^+ (F_{ij}^*)^+) \\ -((T_j^*)^- (T_{ij}^*)^- + (I_j^*)^- (I_{ij}^*)^- + (F_j^*)^- (F_{ij}^*)^-) \end{matrix} \right]} \right)$$

Step 4. Determine the nonincreasing order of $S_i = J_w(b_j^*, b_i)$ $(i = 1, 2, \dots, m)$ $(j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ and select the best alternative.

Now, we give a numerical example as follows;

Example 4.2 Let us consider decision making problem adapted from Xu and Cia [21]. We consider Gaziantep hospital who intends to buy bed. Four types of beds (alternatives) $u_i (i = 1, 2, 3, 4)$ are available. The customer takes into account four attributes to evaluate the alternatives; a_1 = air bed; a_2 = moving bed; a_3 = two motorized bed and use the bipolar neutrosophic values to evaluate the four possible alternatives $u_i (i = 1, 2, 3, 4)$ under the above four attributes. Also, the weight vector of the attributes $a_j (j = 1, 2, 3)$ is $\omega = (0.6, 0.3, 0.1)^T$. Then,

Algorithm

Step1. Constructed the decision matrix provided by the Gaziantep hospital as;

Table 1: Decision matrix given by Hospital

	a_1	a_2	a_3
u_1	$\langle 0.5, 0.7, 0.2, -0.7, -0.3, -0.6 \rangle$	$\langle 0.4, 0.4, 0.5, -0.7, -0.8, -0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.7, 0.7, 0.5, -0.8, -0.7, -0.6 \rangle$
u_2	$\langle 0.9, 0.7, 0.5, -0.7, -0.7, -0.1 \rangle$	$\langle 0.7, 0.6, 0.8, -0.7, -0.5, -0.1 \rangle$	$\langle 0.9, 0.4, 0.6, -0.1, -0.7, -0.5 \rangle$
u_3	$\langle 0.3, 0.4, 0.2, -0.6, -0.3, -0.7 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2, 0.2, 0.2, -0.4, -0.7, -0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.9, 0.5, 0.5, -0.6, -0.5, -0.2 \rangle$
u_4	$\langle 0.9, 0.7, 0.2, -0.8, -0.6, -0.1 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3, 0.5, 0.2, -0.5, -0.5, -0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.5, 0.4, 0.5, -0.1, -0.7, -0.2 \rangle$

Step2. Computed the positive ideal bipolar neutrosophic solution as;

$$b_j^* = \{ \langle 0.9, 0.4, 0.2, -0.8, -0.3, -0.1 \rangle, \langle 0.7, 0.2, 0.2, -0.7, -0.5, -0.1 \rangle, \langle 0.9, 0.4, 0.5, -0.8, -0.5, -0.2 \rangle \}$$

Step3. Calculated the weighted Jaccard vector similarity measures $S_i = J_w(b_j^*, b_i)$ as;

$$S_1 = 0.03126$$

$$S_2 = 0.05809$$

$$S_3 = 0.05033$$

$$S_4 = 0.30225$$

Step4. Rank all the software systems of u ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$.) according to the weighted Jaccard vector similarity measure as;

$$S_2 > S_3 > S_1 > S_4$$

and thus u_2 is the most desirable alternative.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we developed a multi-criteria decision making for bipolar neutrosophic sets based on Jaccard vector similarity measures and applied to a numerical example in order to confirm the practicality and accuracy of the proposed method. In the future, the method can be extend with different similarity and distance measures in fuzzy set, intuitionistic fuzzy set and neutrosophic set.

6. References

- [1] Atanassov, K. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Fuzzy Sets and Systems, 20 (1986) 87-96.
- [2] Broumi, S., Deli, I., Smarandache, F. (2014). Distance and similarity measures of interval neutrosophic soft sets. Critical Review, Center for Mathematics of Uncertainty, Creighton University, USA, 8, 14-31.
- [3] S. Broumi, I. Deli, F. Smarandache, N-valued Interval Neutrosophic Sets and Their Application in Medical Diagnosis, Critical Review, Center for Mathematics of Uncertainty, Creighton University, USA, 10 (2015) 46-69.
- [4] S. Broumi and I. Deli, Correlation measure for neutrosophic Refined sets and its application in medical Diagnosis, Palestine journal of mathematics, 5(1) (2016) , 135–143.
- [5] I. Deli, S. Broumi, F. Smarandache, On neutrosophic refined sets and their applications in medical diagnosis, Journal of New Theory, 6 (2015) 88-98.

- [6] Deli, I., Ali, M., Smarandache, F. (2015, August). Bipolar neutrosophic sets and their application based on multi-criteria decision making problems. In *Advanced Mechatronic Systems (ICAMechS), 2015 International Conference on* (pp. 249-254). IEEE.
- [7] I. Deli “Interval-valued neutrosophic soft sets and its decision making, *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, DOI: 10.1007/s13042-015-0461-3.
- [8] Karaaslan, F. (2016). Correlation Coefficient between Possibility Neutrosophic Soft Sets. *Math. Sci. Lett.* 5, No. 1, 71-74.
- [9] Maji, P. K. (2013). Neutrosophic soft set. *Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics*, 5(1), 157-168.
- [10] Smarandache F (1998) *A Unifying Field in Logics Neutrosophy: Neutrosophic Probability, Set and Logic*. Rehoboth: American Research Press.
- [11] Smarandache F (2005) Neutrosophic set, a generalisation of the intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *Int J Pure Appl Math* 24:287–297.
- [12] Pramanik, S., Mondal, K. (2015). Cosine similarity measure of rough neutrosophic sets and its application in medical diagnosis. *Global Journal of Advanced Research*, 2(1), 212-220.
- [13] H. Wang, F. Smarandache, Y. Q .Zhang, , R. Sunderraman,, Single valued neutrosophic sets, *Multispace and Multistructure*, 4 (2010) 410–413.
- [14] H. Wang, F. Smarandache, Y. Q .Zhang, R. Sunderraman, *Interval Neutrosophic Sets and Logic: Theory and Applications in Computing*, Hexis, Phoenix, AZ, (2005).
- [15] Ye J (2014) Improved correlation coefficients of single valued neutrosophic sets and interval neutrosophic sets for multiple attribute decision making. *J Intell Fuzzy Syst* 27:24532462.
- [16] S. Ye, J. Fu, and J. Ye, Medical Diagnosis Using Distance- Based Similarity Measures of Single Valued Neutrosophic Multisets, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 7 (2015) 47-52.
- [17] J. Ye, ”Similarity measures between interval neutrosophic sets and their multicriteria decision-making method, *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, DOI: 10.3233/IFS-120724.
- [18] S. Ye, J. Ye, Dice similarity measure between single valued neutrosophic multisets and its application in medical diagnosis, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* 6 (2014) 48-52.
- [19] Ye, J. (2014). Vector similarity measures of simplified neutrosophic sets and their application in multicriteria decision making. *International Journal of Fuzzy Systems*, 16(2), 204-215.
- [20] L. A. Zadeh, *Fuzzy Sets, Inform. and Control*, 8 (1965) 338-353.
- [21] Z. Xu, X. Cai, *Intuitionistic Fuzzy Information Aggregation Theory and Applications*, Springer, Science Press, Heidelberg New York Dordrecht London, 2011.